

EOOSC-IF

Guidance note: Writing a Guideline for the EOOSC Interoperability Framework

Version 1.0

May 2023

EOSC-IF / Guidance note: Writing a Guideline for the EOSC Interoperability Framework

Lead by **GÉANT**

Authored by Michelle Williams (GÉANT), Anke Friedrich (GÉANT)

Reviewed by Daan Broeder (CLARIN), Gavin Farrell (ELIXIR/EMBL)

Dissemination Level of the Document

Public

Abstract

This document provides guidance to anyone that would like to propose an Interoperability Guideline for inclusion in the EOSC Interoperability Framework.

This document gives a short overview of the process and provides links to useful resources to help authors of guidelines.

Version History

Version	Date	Authors/Contributors	Description
V0.1	April 2023	Authored by Michelle Williams (GÉANT), Anke Friedrich (GÉANT)	First draft for review by EOSC Future WP3 Participants
V0.2	April 2023	Daan Broeder (CLARIN), Gavin Farrell (ELIXIR/EMBL)	Comments provided
V1.0	May 2023	Michelle Williams (GÉANT), Anke Friedrich (GÉANT)	Final Version published to Zenodo

Copyright Notice

This work by Parties of the EOSC Future Consortium is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). The EOSC Future project is co-funded by the European Union Horizon Programme call INFRAEOSC-03-2020, Grant Agreement number 101017536.

Table of Contents

Glossary	2
List of Abbreviations	2
1 Introduction	3
2 Writing an Interoperability Guideline	3
3 Content and Quality considerations	3
4 Procedural Context	4
5 Proposing a Guideline for Inclusion in the EOSC Interoperability Framework	4
6 Review procedure	5
7 Endorsement procedure	5
8 Dissemination procedure (for approved Guidelines)	5
Related documents	5
References	6

Glossary

EOSC Future project Glossary is incorporated by reference: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/x/JOCK>

List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
EIAB	EOSC Interoperability Advisory Board
EIAC	EOSC Interoperability Area Chairs
EOSC-IF	EOSC Interoperability Framework
EPOT	EOSC Portal Onboarding Team

1 Introduction

The EOSC-IF will be built upon a wide range of components, such as standards, APIs, policy frameworks, etc. Starting with human-readable interoperability guidelines that aim to promote and facilitate interoperability across services, resources, infrastructures and domains, the Framework will begin to incorporate more executable, machine-readable artefacts that would support composable or executable workflows at a later stage. Guidance and positioning is offered to owners, maintainers and authors of Interoperability Guidelines both in respect of within the EOSC environment and within the scientific community at large.

It is assumed that Interoperability Guidelines will be already established and published by an Infrastructure or Scientific Domain/Community, and, therefore, an author will not intend to write a new Interoperability Guideline for submission to the EOSC Interoperability Framework. However, it is conceivable that an existing Interoperability Guideline or collection of Guidelines would benefit from being structured into an EOSC Interoperability Guideline. In this case, a Word template has been provided¹ that is tailored towards Interoperability Guidelines produced under the EOSC Future project, but that can also be utilised (ensuring that the relevant copyright and project funding statements are updated as required), and the following guidance notes can be utilised in producing that document.

2 Writing an Interoperability Guideline

- When writing an EOSC Interoperability Guideline, it is important that authors take into consideration and adhere to the information given in the template, although authors are entitled to flex the template and its branding to fit their needs, or to use an existing document/template from their own Infrastructure or Community, provided that it does not result in the omission of key sections of information that has been included in the EOSC Interoperability Guideline template.
- Care should be taken to ensure that the correct copyright and funding statements are included in the resulting document.
- The Guideline must meet the Inclusion Criteria²; this will also become available at the EOSC Providers Hub³. It is important that the proposer of the Interoperability Guideline consults the Inclusion Criteria before making their submission.
- The resulting Interoperability Guideline must be reviewed within its own context and community, and published in a repository that meets the related Inclusion Criteria before its registration as an EOSC Interoperability Guideline, however, it's conceivable that the EOSC-IF Guideline Review procedure might identify and propose some adjustments that might require a new version to be published.

3 Content and Quality Considerations

Ideally the Guideline would be reusable, and would be a 'recipe for an interoperability solution listing protocols, standards and formats in a machine readable way' (as opposed to a Guideline that promotes only one standard, format, protocol, etc.), that would allow allow (research) service or workflow implementation with specific interoperability goals in mind, that is, to understand boundary conditions of related services and ecosystems, to establish rules for interoperating at the edges of those boundaries, and to serve ideally as an example for work where interoperability problems have been solved.

Authors or proposers of Interoperability Guidelines should aim to incorporate the following characteristics:

Clear and Concise: The guideline should be easy to follow, using clear and concise language. Authors should take care to ensure the correct level of technical detail is provided and should avoid use of jargon that is difficult for users to understand.

¹ <https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-interoperability-framework/eosc-if-templates-and-information>

²

<https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/EOSCSMS/EOSC-Exchange+inclusion+criteria#EOSCExchangeinclusioncriteria-3.6.Additionalinclusioncriteriaonboardaninteroperabilityguideline>

³ <https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-providers-hub>

Comprehensive: The guideline should be self-contained by default, covering all relevant aspects of creating or configuring the interoperability solution, including technical standards, protocols, data formats, and interfaces, in order to make it practical and feasible to implement. However, existing widely accepted documentation of standards etc. should be referenced rather than copied.

Adaptable: The guideline should be flexible enough to accommodate changes and updates as new technologies and standards emerge.

Consistent: If the guideline references another, it should be consistent with the referenced guideline with direct references to the relevant version. It should not contradict or replicate the referenced guideline. References/dependencies (and their explicit versions) must be declared in the related standards table.

User-Centred: The guideline should be designed with a specific implementer audience in mind, and should set out clearly the characteristics of that audience.

Well-Tested: The guideline should be well-tested and validated through practical use cases and scenarios.

The Provider of an Interoperability Guideline assumes the responsibility to maintain it, in the sense that it should be reviewed and updated throughout its serviceable life when needed.

Where an Interoperability Guideline relates to a workflow, practice, service or software product, the Guideline should be updated in line with the workflow, practice, service or software product update.

Overall, an Interoperability Guideline should provide clear and actionable guidance that helps users achieve interoperability in a consistent and efficient manner.

4 Procedural Context

1. **Proposing a Guideline for Inclusion in the EOSC Interoperability Framework** - Proposer requests inclusion of new guidelines to be included in the EOSC IF; refer to the Guidance Notes on Onboarding a Guideline to the EOSC Interoperability Framework⁴.
2. **Review procedure** - New requests are reviewed in terms of technical quality and clarity, and are assessed as to whether they are consistent with the expectation of EOSC IF guidelines.
3. **Endorsement procedure** - New guidelines are discussed within the EIAC and if approved submitted to the EIAB for endorsement.
4. **Dissemination procedure** - Adopted guidelines are announced via the EOSC channels.

5 Proposing a Guideline for Inclusion in the EOSC Interoperability Framework.

The Author/Owner may propose a Guideline for Inclusion in the EOSC Interoperability Framework. This is initiated by the proposer by onboarding a new Interoperability Guideline Profile via the EOSC Providers Portal⁵, which will trigger an Onboarding Procedure via the EPOT channels.

Further details of procedures are provided here for the purposes of informing the Author/Owner of a Guideline as to what happens subsequent to submission of a proposed Interoperability Guideline.

⁴ Guidance note: Onboarding an Interoperability Guideline to EOSC: [10.5281/zenodo.7929834](https://zenodo.org/record/105281)

⁵ <https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/home>

6 Review Procedure

- The EIAC Chair creates an endorsement request page for the guideline on the appropriate wiki (currently <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EIAB+and+EIAC+Charter>) and links the guideline in using its URI starting <https://doi...>
- The EIAC Chair finds volunteer reviewers to appraise the proposed Guideline. This can be achieved either by hosting regular meetings or by requesting volunteers via email to the eiac@eoscfuture.eu mailing list.
- The reviewers examine the quality of the submitted guideline and metadata referring to the Inclusion Criteria and the general recommendations and guidance set out in the template. This may include spelling, accuracy, composition, and URLs, but the reviewers will not perform interoperability tests as a matter of routine.
- The reviewers write their comments in the appropriate position on the related endorsement page filling in the first four columns of the Comment/Change log.
- During this procedure, the reviewers or the EIAC Chair may request evidence that the Guideline has been verified, and that it is mature within the Infrastructure, Domain or Community that proposed it.
- The authors must reply to any queries, and in some cases may be asked to make changes to the Guideline documentation, and to provide an updated version of the documentation before it can be endorsed.
- The Reviewers fill in the table 'Statements of Support/Deny'.

7 Endorsement Procedure

- Based on the outcome of the Review Procedure, the remaining EIAC members fill in the table 'Statements of Support/Deny'.
- All responses (support/deny) are treated as votes as whether or not to accept the Guideline into the EOSC Interoperability Framework. This may take place either during a 'Interoperability Guideline Review Meeting' or via email.
- The outcome of the vote becomes a recommendation to the EIAB made by the EIAC Chair.
- The EIAB may have additional comments, and will approve or reject the proposed Guideline.
- The EIAC Chair will contact the Author/Owner to inform them of the outcome.

8 Dissemination Procedure (for approved Guidelines)

- The authors make final changes to the guideline and submit the final version to the EIAC Chair.
 - **[end of action for authors]**
- EIAC Chair and EPOT team progresses the Onboarding workflow to publish the Guideline's Profile and marks it as 'Accepted'.
- The EIAC Chair informs the EOSC Future Outreach/Communications team that a new Interoperability Guideline is available, and this can be communicated in the next EOSC Future newsletter.

Related documents

- Guidance note: Onboarding an Interoperability Guideline to EOSC: 10.5281/zenodo.7929834
- Guidance note: Assigning an Interoperability Guideline to an EOSC Service Profile: 10.5281/zenodo.7929856
- Guidance note: Reviewing a Guideline for the EOSC Interoperability Framework: 10.5281/zenodo.7929900
- EPOT Procedure-14: Onboard an Interoperability Guideline (relating to EPOT team activities).⁶

⁶

<https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/EOSCOB/EPOT+Procedure-14%3A+Onboard+an+Interoperability+Guideline>

References

- [1] EOSC Interoperability Framework, online. Available at <https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-interoperability-framework/>
- [2] EOSC Onboarding Inclusion Criteria, [online] Available at: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/EOSCSMS/EOSC-Exchange+inclusion+criteria>
- [3] EOSC Interoperability Framework Inclusion Criteria, 2023, online. Available at: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/EOSCSMS/EOSC-Exchange+inclusion+criteria#EOSCExchangeinclusioncriteria-3.6.Additionalinclusioncriteriatoonboardaninteroperabilityguideline>
- [4] EOSC Portal Providers Hub, online. Available at <https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-providers-hub>
- [5] EIAC and EIAB Charter, online. Available at <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EIAB+and+EIAC+Charter>
- [6] Eosc-portal.eu. 2021. EOSC Portal. [online] Available at: <<https://eosc-portal.eu/>>